

Look

Body movement

Shoulder

Chest

Abdomen

Listen

Sound of air
Breathing in & out

Normal

Fast

Slow

Noisy

Agonal

Feel

Air on our cheek

Is the situation
safe for me?

Safety

1. Can you write in your own words what dangers you have to look out for?
2. What would you have done if there were a fire around the victim?
3. Why is it important to look for dangers?

Is the situation safe for
those around me?

Safety

1. What do you think you need to look out for?
2. What would happen if the people around you were in danger?
3. Would it be better to start with the bystander CPR without looking for safety first?

Is the person
in need safe?

Safety

1. Describe a safe environment for the victim.
2. Can you elaborate on the reason that you have to watch out for traffic?
3. What would you have done if there was heavy traffic around the victim?

Kneel by the side of the
victim

Check for Response

1. What is the first step when checking for response?
2. What is the main idea of this step?
3. When would you end this step?

Gently shake / touch
shoulders and ask
"Are you alright"?

Check for Response

1. What action can you add to make sure that the person is not responding?
2. What would result if you acted without checking for response?
3. Make a scenario to show how it works.

If the victim is not reacting (for example speaking or reacting to you), check for normal breathing

Check for normal breathing

1. What might happen if the victim does not react? What should you do then?
2. How do you recommend to check for normal breathing?
3. Why do you need to check for normal breathing?

Place your hand on
the forehead and the
fingertips of your
other hand under the
point of the chin

Check for normal breathing

1. What do you have to do with the victim's head first?
2. Give a reason for placing the head in this position.
3. Predict which part of the head you should pay attention to next.

Gently tilt the
victim's head
backwards, lifting the chin
to open the
airway

Check for normal breathing

1. Can you explain what is happening in this picture?
2. What is the motive behind this position?
3. What made the position of the first responder successful?

Place your head over the
victim's head

Check for normal breathing

1. Recall the first sense you have to use to check the breathing.

2. Describe your physical position.

3. Suppose you cannot see the moving chest. How can you improve the situation?

LOOK if the chest is
moving

Check for normal breathing

1. Can you distinguish between this step and the previous step?
2. Would it be better if you only LOOKED to check for normal breathing?
3. What went well in this situation?

LISTEN with your ear for
respiratory sounds

Check for normal breathing

1. What action of control do you see on this picture?
2. What do you think the first responder would listen for?
3. What were the advantages of this step?

FEEL the victim's
breath on your
cheek

Check for normal breathing

1. What does it mean if you feel the victim's breath?
2. How is the victim's breath and CPR connected?
3. Why is it important to feel the victim's breath and not just look and listen for it?

10"

Having looked,
listened and felt for
up to 10 seconds, ask
yourself "Is this nor-
mal breathing OR is it
only coughing, moaning,
snoring?"

Check for normal breathing

1. What questions would you ask yourself in this situation?
2. Would it be better if the victim were breathing very slowly?
3. Do you agree that coughing is a sign of normal breathing?

If the victim is unresponsive and/or not breathing, or is breathing abnormally, ask a helper to call the emergency services or call them yourself

Call for Help

1. What do you do when no other person is around you?
2. What might happen if you do not call the emergency services now?
3. How would you improve this situation?

Stay with the
victim while calling for
help, if possible

Call for Help

1. Should you stay with the victim when calling for help?
2. Can you identify the main idea why you have to stay with the victim?
3. What are pros and cons of staying with the victim?

Call for Help

1. Which number do you have to dial?
2. How would you classify the importance of this step?
3. How would you end this situation?

Activate the
speaker function of the
phone, if possible

Call for Help

1. What does this symbol stand for?
2. Do you think switching on the speaker is a good thing here?
3. What could be an advantage of using the speaker function? In which situation?

Name?

Location?

What happened?

.....?

Say your name,
your location and what
happened, and answer
the questions that are
asked on the phone

Call for Help

1. What would the emergency services ask you in this situation?
2. How would you feel if you were in this situation?
3. How would you improve the situation while making the call?

Stay on the phone, don't
hang up

Call for Help

1. Is it okay to hang up, after answering the questions?
2. Can you identify the main ideas of staying on the phone?
3. How do you think you would feel in this situation?

Send a helper to bring
an AED, if applicable.
If you are alone, do not
leave the victim,
but start CPR

Call for Help

1. Which one should go to bring an AED?
2. How can you attract a bystander's attention to help you?
3. Can you predict the outcome if you went to bring the AED yourself?

Place the heel of your
hand on the center of
the victim's chest

Chest compressions

1. Describe the position of the first responder's hand?
2. Why is it important not to place the hand on the belly?
3. Would you remove clothes from the victim's upper body or not?

Place the heel of
the other hand on the
top of the first
hand and interlock
your fingers

Chest compressions

1. How many hands do you need for the following step?
2. Do you agree with the action of interlocking the fingers?
3. Why did Marco choose to position his hands like this?

Keep your arms straight

Chest compressions

1. Why should you keep your arms straight during chest compressions?
2. How do you check if your arms are straight?
3. Would it be better if your arms were angled?

Position yourself
vertically above the
victim's chest and press
down on the sternum,
5-6cm

Chest compressions

1. Can you recall how deep you have to press your arms?
2. Based on what you know, how would you explain the depth of the press?
3. What would happen if you were not strong enough?

After each
compression,
release the pressure
on the chest,
without losing
contact between your
hand and the sternum

Chest compressions

1. What happens after each chest compression?
2. Elaborate on the reason of the release.
3. Is it an advantage or a disadvantage to leave your hands on the breastbone of the victim?

Repeat at a rate
of 100-120
compressions per min

Chest compressions

1. Provide a short outline of the next action.
2. Compose a song about the beat of the chest compressions.
3. Would you recommend a compression faster than 100-120 beats per minute?

After 30 compressions, open the airway, pinch the soft part of the nose closed, using the index finger and thumb of your hand on the victim's forehead. Allow the victim's mouth to open

Ventilation

1. After how many compressions do you ventilate?
2. Can you identify the main events of the action in this picture?
3. Can you think of another suitable title for this action?

Take a normal breath and
place your lips around the
victim's mouth,
making sure you have an
airtight seal

Ventilation

1. What is Marco doing here?
2. Do you take a normal breath in this situation or stronger than normal?
3. How do you make sure that all the air is going into the person's mouth?

Blow steadily into the mouth whilst watching for the chest to rise for about 1 second

Ventilation

1. What would you have done in the same situation?
2. Can you propose an alternative if you do not want to ventilate?
3. How many seconds would you blow into the victim's mouth for?

Take another normal
breath and repeat it once
more (2 breaths in total)!

Ventilation

1. How many times do you have to blow into the victim's mouth?
2. Why did the ventilation happen?
3. What is your opinion on ventilation?

Continue with chest compressions and rescue breaths at a ratio of 30:2 until help arrives!

Ventilation

1. What does the action on the pictures look like?
2. What is the relationship between the compressions and the ventilation?
3. Why is it important to start chest compressions again?

Look around you for the
AED sign

AED deployment

1. Can you list three elements of the AED sign?
2. Can you identify possible locations for AEDs?
3. Based on what you know, how would you explain what an AED sign looks like?

If there is a second helper, one of you should get an AED, the other should continue CPR on the victim

AED deployment

1. How many people do you need to use an AED?
2. How would you rate the importance of using an AED?
3. How would you organise further steps if there were enough people to use an AED?

If no AED is available,
continue CPR

AED deployment

1. Can you stop the compressions the during this step?
2. Why do you think it is important not to stop compressions?
3. What would happen if you stopped the compressions?

If you see a person
holding their hand
around their throat
and coughing

Foreign Body Airway Obstruction

1. Can you explain what is happening here?
2. Why did this situation happen?
3. What is the best solution to the problem?

then encourage that
person to cough

Foreign Body Airway Obstruction

1. What would you do in the same situation?
2. Identify the main idea behind the action of the first responder.
3. Is it important to demonstrate to the person how it is done?

If the person is unable
to speak and is
struggling or
unable to breathe

Foreign Body Airway Obstruction

1. How is the choking person feeling?
2. Can you make use of the facts to choose the further steps?
3. What would you have done to help the person?

then support their chest with one hand, lean them forward and apply 5 blows between their shoulder blades with the heel of your other hand

Foreign Body Airway Obstruction

1. Explain what Marco is doing in the picture.
2. What would you have done in the same situation?
3. Imagine you are one of the characters and write a diary entry.

Music Games

Fingers or Palms?

Experiment clapping in two ways:

a) with two fingers of one hand hitting two fingers of the other

or

b) with cupped palms of both hands

Which of the following is your friend clapping?

1. fingers, fingers, palms, palms
2. palms, palms, fingers, fingers
3. fingers, palms, fingers, palms
4. palms, fingers, palms, fingers

Music Games

Where is the Clapper?

You are in the center of the circle made by all members of your group.

They stand side by side, facing you.

Close your eyes for a moment so that the leader can point to the participant who will be the 'clapper'.

Open your eyes.

All participants sing a song together and pretend to clap their hands behind their back.

Only the clapper is actually clapping.

Listen carefully, can you find the clapper?

Level 1

VP-01

Identify the objects from
the shapes.

Identify the objects from
the shapes.

Level 2

VP-02

Name the opposite direction to each arrow.

Name each letter.

b	q	p	d
p	b	q	p
d	q	p	q
p	d	b	p
b	q	d	b
q	p	p	b

Level 1/2

AP-01

Auditory Perception

- Close your eyes and identify who is talking.
- Describe the speech.

Loud / Quiet

High / Deep voice

Fast / Slow

- Close your eyes and identify who is talking.
- Describe the speech.

High / Low volume

High / Low pitch

Fast / Slow speed

Lively / Flat intonation

Level 2

AP-02

Auditory Perception

- Close your eyes.
- Listen to the speech by your classmate.

-
- Describe the speech volume (high, low)
speed (fast, slow)
pitch (high, low)
pauses (frequent, infrequent)
 - Can you guess the person who is speaking?

Level 1

AT-01

Attention

- Choose a letter.
- Write as many words as you can, starting with that letter.
- You have 1 minute.
- Use the word categories on the other side of the card for help.

Jungle animals

Winter clothes

Pets

Cooking utensils

Furniture

Tools

Transportation means

School accessories

Body parts

Musical instruments

Electronic devices

Professions

Level 2

AT-02

Attention

- Climb down the ladder, two stairs at a time, from 100 to 80, as fast as you can. The ladder will help you.

- Climb down the ladder, three stairs at a time, from 100 to 70, as fast as you can. The ladder will help you.

Level 2

AT-03

Attention

Say as fast as you can

3

3

2

3

in the following
situations

You are in a stadium
You are downtown
You are in a village
You are on a beach
You are at a supermarket
You are at a pharmacy
You are at a gas station
You are at a bakery
You are at a hospital
You are at restaurant
You are at a garage

“What happened?” shouted Mike upset and started to run towards him. At the same time, Nick looked at the collapsed caretaker frozen and Anne turned around ready to start running. “Mike, stop! We need to approach safely. We don’t know what has happened!”, said Kate decisively.

-
- Count the words in the text as fast as you can, without reading them.
 - Don't point at the words with your finger.
 - Count the words again and check if the word counts match.

Level 1

ME-01

Memory

You will have 30
seconds to
remember everything you
can about the picture.

Level 1

ME-02

Memory

Remember the items.

Remember the items.

Level 1

ME-03

Memory

Remember the items.

Identify the items.

Level 1

ME-04

Memory

Remember the order of the objects.

Remember the order of the objects.

Level 1

ME-05

Observe and memorize
the objects within 1 min.

Which objects are missing from the picture?

Level 2

ME-06

Memory

Remember the order of the objects.

Remember the order of the objects.

Level 2

ME-07

Memory

Memorize the items.

Identify the items.

Level 2

ME-08

Memory

Memorize the items.

Memorize the items.

Level 2

ME-09

Memory

You will have 30
seconds to
remember everything you
can about the picture.

Memory

How to remember what I hear.

1. Picture what I hear
2. Break up what I hear in small parts

3. Focus on the important information I hear
**who, when, where,
what, how, why**

4. Ask the teacher to repeat what they said if I don't remember something

Cause-Effect

- Find the causes for the following effects

The sky is gray, **because**

We put things in bags,

Plants bloom,

At school the bell rings,

Earth globes are useful,

Sometimes it's hard to
wake up,

We can see the rainbow,

- Find the effects for the following causes

Yesterday it snowed, **so**

You jogged for an hour,

Our fridge was broken,

You studied hard the whole year,

Your sister broke your favourite toy,

You broke your hand,

You had a fight with your friend,

Cause-Effect

1. Listen to the story
2. Choose a phrase from the back side
3. Fill in the gaps (orally/in writing)

. because

. . . , so

The cause is

. causes

. . . happens because. . .

. as a result of

If., the end of the
story

Level 1/2

CT-03

Decision making

- Choose one option:
Paper book or E-book
Bicycle or Scooter
Volleyball or Basketball
Art or Science
Flat or House
Museum or Library
Summer or Winter
Outdoor or video games
Adventure or Comedy

- Justify your decision
(give 2-3 reasons)
- Use the phrases to
present your decision

I believe that

I choose

My decision is

I prefer

I decided

I select

Logical Reasoning

- Answer the questions

Can you glue paper
without glue?

Can you sleep during the
day?

Can bears walk on two
legs?

Can you see in the dark?

Can it rain if it is sunny?

Can you sing without
opening your mouth?

- Fill in the following sentences

Knife is to cutting, as

a. pencil to _____

b. bed to _____

Oil comes from olives, as

a. wine from _____

b. jam from _____

Book is made of paper, as

a. shoes of _____

b. clothes of _____

Logical Reasoning

- Which is always/
sometimes/never true?

A sailboat has a motor

A bookcase has books

Shoes have soles

A watch tells the time

Carrots grow on trees

A race has a finish line

A tree has roots

Locks open with keys

A calendar tells the time

- Complete the word pairs
with the proper words

sand:desert - water:_____

letters:word - words:_____

spring:March - _____:June

soccer:eleven - basket:___

skiing:outdoor - __:indoor

wheel:car - branch:_____

pupil:school - player:_____

boat:harbor - car:_____

car:boot - trousers:_____

Argumentation

Make arguments with the following structure

1. Give your opinion

I think, I believe, I prefer

In my opinion, I feel

2. Provide reasons

To start with, Firstly,

Secondly, Next,

Another reason,

Most importantly,

Lastly, Finally

3. Give examples/details

For example, Additionally,
In fact, An example is,
In other words,
Specifically, In particular

4. Come to a conclusion

To sum up, To conclude,
As you can see,
In conclusion, Finally,
To summarize

Argumentation

Choose one option from each pair on the other side and:

- Which of the 2 options do you choose?
- Give 3 reasons to support your choice
- Give 3 reasons why you didn't choose the other option

Train or Airplane
Winter or Summer
Savoury or Sweets
Hotel or Camping
Car or Motorcycle
Book or Movie
Sports or Arts
Desert or Jungle
Solo sport or Team sport
Travel to the past or
Travel to the future
Fly or Be invisible

Level 1

CT-08

Problem solving

How to solve problems

1. What is the problem?
2. Ask questions/get information
3. Find solutions

How to get information

- Ask

why....?

who....?

what....?

when....?

where....?

Problem solving

How to solve problems

1. What is the problem?
2. What are some solutions?
3. Ask yourself:
is it safe for me, how might people feel about it, is it fair, will it work?
4. Choose a solution.
5. If not successful, what can I do now?

- What will you do?

Someone has something that you want.

You cut a finger opening a tin can.

You see someone hit by a car crossing the street.

Your grandmother suddenly has trouble speaking.

A friend is mad at you, but you don't know why.

Level 1

CT-10

Compare - Contrast

Answer the questions.

What are the similarities?

What are the differences?

What else tastes sour?

Which other fruits we
peel?

Answer the questions.

What are the similarities?

What are the differences?

Name means of mass
transportation.

Name means of individual
transportation.

Level 2

CT-11

Compare - Contrast

Answer the questions.

What are the similarities?

What are the differences?

Name other places of residence.

Name tall buildings or landmarks in Europe.

Answer the questions.

What are the similarities?
What are the differences?
Name things we weigh.
Name things that are
frozen or hot.

Level 1

Orientation

Left

OR-01

Right

-
- Choose any object/
symbol from your
handbook/classroom.
 - Put your hands on
either side of it.
 - Name other objects to
the left/right of that
object.
 - Name which side the
symbols are facing.

Level 1/2

OR-02

Orientation

- Choose an object in your classroom.
- Use the following words to describe where it is located.

Over / Under

Between

Next to

Behind

In front of

To the right of

To the left of

Level 1/2

OR-03

Orientation

Before

- Imagine what happened
before

Brush your teeth

Offer a present

Eat a meal

Take a shower

Bake a cake

Ride your bicycle

Do your homework

Level 1/2

OR-04

Orientation

After

- Imagine what will happen
after

Return from school

Eat ice cream

Water the plants

Walk the dog

Read a book

Have an accident

Wash your hands

Non-verbal communication

- Listen to the conversation between your classmates.
- Was there non-verbal communication?
- Identify non-verbal features and note which were missing.

The features on the other side of the card can help you.

facial expressions
eye contact
body movement
gestures
pauses
volume, pitch, and tone
of voice
distance between talking
pupils
touch

Prosody

- Choose one option from the other side of the card.
- Use the voice of the character you chose.
- Read the sentences / story you are given.

Monster

Mad scientist

Old person

Pirate

Mouse

Baby

Robot

Quick pace

Slow pace

Silly voice

Nasal voice

Whispering voice

Level 1

CS-03

Conversational skills

1. Choose a topic.

What makes a good friend?

What magic power do you wish you had? why?

If you could go anywhere where would you go? why?

Which cartoon character would you be?

2. Turn over the card.

3. Have a conversation following the rules.

Conversational rules

Start with a "W" question

Look at the other person

Take turns (don't interrupt)

Stay on topic

Make a comment

To change the topic, wait for a break

End the conversation
(i.e. see you soon)

Open-ended questions

- Listen to the story.
- Read the answers written on the whiteboard.
- Find the correct question to each answer, using the questions on the other side of the card.

Questions

How do you know that...?

What did (hero) do first?

What do you think would happen if/after/next...?

How did that happen?

What could (hero) do instead?

What else can (hero) use?

What else is like this?

Why did (hero) choose that?

Level 2

CS-05

Conversation check list

Non-verbal

communication

Turn taking/interrupting

Focus on the speaker

Questions on the topic

Change of subjects

Conversation finish

- Answer the questions

How do you start a conversation?

How can you show you are actively listening?

Why should you wait for your turn to speak?

What do you do when you have not understood something?

How would you close a conversation?

Description

- Describe the object

What is its name?

Where can we find it?

What is its color and shape?

What is its material?

How is it used?

Do you have one yourself?

How would you use it?

- Describe a person

Who is this person?

How do you know this person?

How is this person (face, body)?

What are they wearing?

What is their job?

Where do they work?

Description

- Describe the object

Name this object and specify its type

Where can we find it?

What are its characteristics?

What is it made of?

How is it used?

Have you ever used it?

Name similar objects

- Describe a person

What is their name?

What is your relationship with them?

What are their physical characteristics?

What is their appearance?

What is their profession?

How do they behave?

What do you feel for them?

Description

- Describe a location

What is its name?

Where is it located?

How does it look like?

Why do we go there?

Where is a similar location?

How do you feel when you go there?

- Describe a situation

Who are the heroes?

Where is it happening?

When did it happen?

What is happening?

How are the heroes acting?

How are they feeling?

What happened in the end?

Name a similar situation that happened to you?

Narrative

- Listen to/read a story.
- Find the following information.

WHO is/are the hero(es)
of the story

SETTING where/when does
the story take place

WHAT do the heroes want
to achieve

PROBLEM(S) to solve

- Narrate or draw a story.
- Use the structure.

BEGINNING who, where,
when

PROBLEM what happened

BUILD UP how is the
problem solved

RESOLUTION what solution
was given to the problem

ENDING achievements/
conclusions

Narrative writing check list

- Include a beginning, a middle and an ending
- Create a setting:
who, what, where/when
- Create a problem
- Provide actions for
problem solution
- Solve the problem
- Write a proper ending

Use these words:

to begin a paragraph

at first, first of all, to
begin, in the first place

inside a paragraph

for this reason, then, soon
earlier, also, next, usually
later, while, except, yet

to end a paragraph

finally, the next step, on
the whole, as a result, for
now

Processing speed

- Choose one of the following lists.

Letters of the alphabet

Days of the week

Seasons of the year

Months of the year

- Then, follow the instructions on the other side.

- Start from a different element in the list.

Continue until the end of the list.

- Start from a different element in the list.

Go backwards.

Continue until you have said all elements of the list.

Level 1

PS-02

Name the animal and do
NOT read the word.

Name the animal and do
NOT read the word.

Duck

Frog

Dog

Dinosaur

Penguin

Turtle

Sheep

Swan

Camel

Hare

Elephant

Kangaroo

Level 1/2

PS-03

Name one shape, then one color alternately.

Name one number, then
one colour alternately.

3	0	7	1
4	2	9	6
5	8	3	0
7	1	4	2
9	6	5	8
1	7	6	3

Level 2

PS-04

Processing speed

- Say backwards what you hear from your classmate.

- Read out the following slowly.

3 - 5 - 8

table-bike-boat

2 - 6 - 7 - 9

mouse-basket-road-light

14 - 21

acrobat-tennis-spaghetti

18 - 30 - 3

pear-capital-small-class

10 - 23 - 87